

Promoting Geothermal District Heating Systems in Europe

Geothermal District Heating Market Development (FINAL VERSION November 2014)

Historical development

- The use of geothermal for district heating (DH) purposes is all but new. It dates back to Roman ages, while a DH system pioneered in year 1330 at Chaudes Aigues, in Central France and fed by the Par hot spring at 82°C is still operating to date.
- In Iceland, where today 95% of buildings are heated with geothermal, extensive distribution of hot water for heating homes began in 1930 in the area of Reykjavik. Outside the EU-28, Iceland is still the leading country with more than 2 GWth installed.
- Doublet systems were developed and used for the first time in France in the 1960s, and then in Eastern Germany in 1984. As a response to the two oil crisis of the 1970s, several other countries in search of alternative sources of energy installed GeoDH systems.
- Cheaper oil in the 1990s temporarily decelerated the growth of GeoDH in Europe. However, with technological development, a new increase in fossil fuel prices, as well as sustainability and security supply concerns the GeoDH market has enjoyed a renewed momentum in the last 5 years.

Installed capacity, by country (MWth), EU-28, 2014

- In 2014 there are 247 geothermal plants supplying district heating networks in 22 European countries Europe, with a total installed capacity of 4.500 MWth.
- The 162 GeoDH systems installed in the EU-28 display a total installed capacity of 1.3 GWth. France is the leading country with 319 MWth installed, followed by Germany (270 MWth), and Hungary (198 MWth).

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Development in GeoDH countries, 2011-2014-2018

France: 5 new projects entered into operation during the GeoDH project and two plants have been upgraded with triplet systems; 45 projects are being planned, many of which are CHP.

Germany: 5 new plants online during the GeoDH project, other 44 under are being developed.

Hungary: 5 new plants in operation between 2011 and 2014, other 21 will be operation by 2018.

Italy: 3 new plants in the last three years and ten new in the next years.

Netherlands: 5 new plants since 2011, all of them for supply heat for horticulture. Other 4 projects are under construction.

Denmark: One new plant was inaugurated in 2013 in Sønderborg, while 10 are under development.

One new project since 2011 entered into operation in both **Slovakia and Poland** where 7 and 2 new projects respectively should be realised in the next years.

Although no new plants have been finalised during these years, compared to 2011 there are new more projects in several emerging countries: **Czech Republic (1), Romania (2), UK (2 new projects and a new regulatory framework under preparation), and Slovenia (2).**

No relevant development was observed in **Bulgaria and Ireland.**

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- In the EU France has the highest number (45) of systems installed, followed by Germany (25) Hungary (21), and Italy (19). These three markets are still developing.
- A very promising growth is observed in the Netherlands and Denmark. In both cases risk mitigation schemes will be in place in the next years. Overall, there is evidence of deep geothermal development in 22 EU countries.

Number of GeoDH Systems

- Traditionally, major GeoDH sites have been developed in areas enjoying high enthalpy resources. However, these systems can also be developed in low and medium enthalpy fields. Several systems work with low temperatures supported by large heat pumps, which favour the development of systems in more European countries.
- Cogeneration geothermal plants are operating in Iceland, but also in Austria and Germany with medium temperatures driving binary turbines. Geothermal CHP plants are being developed also in Hungary and France. In the future, cogeneration can help geothermal to become more economically attractive by recovering waste heat then distributed through district systems for heating and cooling purposes.
- A new route for GeoDH is through the development of Enhanced Geothermal Systems. In November 2012 drilling works were inaugurated at the Ecogi project in Alsace. The 24-MWth project is the first exclusively aiming to provide geothermal process heat to industry.

Technological developments